

Observations and Modeling of the 'Frozen-In Anticyclone' in the 2005 Arctic Summer Stratosphere

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Observing the FrIAC

(Pronounced "Freak")

- Spin-up Phase (March – early April)
- Anticyclonic Phase (Early April – May)
- Shearing Phase (June – August)

Modeling the FrIAC

- GMI-Aura4
- GMI-Aura5
- GMI-MERRA-Replay
- VITA

Summary/Conclusions

VITA N₂O at 850 K on 18 April 2005

Defining The Phases of the FrIAC

2005 Zonal Mean Wind at 850 K (~32 km)

Latitudinal
Range of the
FrIAC

- Phase 1: Spin-up (March – early April 2005)
- Phase 2: Anticyclonic Phase (early April – May 2005)
- Phase 3: Shearing Phase (June – August 2005)

Phase I: Spin-up (March – Early April 2005)

MLS N₂O at 850 K

GEOS-5 PV at 850 K

MLS N2O 850 K 20050301

EPV 850 K 20050301

N₂O Mixing Ratio [ppbv]

EPV [PV units]

White contours are geopotential height at 10 hPa

Phase I: Spin-up (March – Early April 2005)

PV 04 April 520 K

PV 04 April 580 K

PV 04 April 650 K

PV 04 April 740 K

PV 04 April 850 K

PV 04 April 960 K

PV 04 April 1100 K

PV 04 April 1300 K

PV (color) and height (white) anomalies extend from 580 to 1100 K (~25-40 km)

Cross-Polar Advection: 8-14 April

MLS 20050408

MLS 20050410

MLS 20050412

MLS 20050414

- From 8-14 April, the FrIAC crosses directly over the North Pole
- This is partially obscured in the MLS data, which only extends to 82° N
- Interesting case study of cross-polar transport.

Phase II: Anticyclonic Phase (Mid-April to May 2005)

MLS N₂O at 850 K

GEOS-5 PV at 850 K

MLS N2O 850 K 20050415

EPV 850 K 20050415

The PV anomaly vanishes by 1 June due to radiative effects
The N₂O anomaly is relatively undiminished

Vertical Tilting of N₂O Anomaly

GMI Aura4 N₂O at 74° N (deviation from the zonal mean)

1 May 2005 (Anomaly is vertically Upright)

30 June 2005 (Anomaly is tilted)

- Anomaly is vertically upright through April and most of May
- Vertical tilting starts in late May, westward tilt with height
- Steep tilting occurs in June-July, enhancing vertical diffusion

Phase III: Shear Phase (June – August)

MLS N₂O at 850 K

GEOS-5 PV at 850 K

N₂O anomaly shears in both horizontal and vertical.
Anomaly eventually homogenizes with the ambient air.

Modeling the FrlAC

Global Modeling Initiative (GMI)-Aura 4 (Offline CTM)

- Met fields: GEOS-4 Data Assimilation System
- 2° lat x 2.5° lon x 42 levels (lid at 0.01 hPa)
- Time period: Feb. 2004 – Dec. 2006

GMI-Aura 5 (Offline CTM)

- Met Fields: GEOS-5.1 Data Assimilation System
- 2° lat x 2.5° lon x 72 levels (lid at 0.01 hPa)

GMI-Merra Replay (Online)

- Met Fields: MERRA
- 2° lat x 2.5° lon x 72 levels (lid at 0.01 hPa)
- “Online” constituents

Van leer Icosahedral Triangular Advection (VITA) Model

- Met Fields: GEOS-5
- Triangular grid at 20 km resolution
- 2-D isentropic offline simulation
- Initialized with MLS N₂O

Modeling the FrIAC with GMI

Phase 1: Spin-Up (4 April 2005)

GMI :

- Produces the FrIAC from 650 – 960 K.
- Peak N₂O mixing ratios in GMI are smaller than MLS.

Cross-Polar Advection (740 K shown, approximately 29 km)

MLS

GMI-Aura4

VITA

- From 8-14 April, the FrIAC crosses directly over the North Pole
- GMI-Aura4 does poorly with cross-polar advection
- VITA triangular-grid model simulates cross-polar advection well.

Cross-Polar Flow in GMI

Black circles indicate size of polar cap.

Large drop in N₂O (19% reduction of peak)

Small drop in N₂O (1% reduction of peak)

Longitude vs. Time Plots at 850 K, 78° N

Mar 1

Apr 1

May 1

Jun 1

Jul 1

Aug 1

**Black contours are
from MERRA-Replay**

Modeling the Shearing Phase (June – August)

Simulations at 850 K, 1 June – 31 August 2005

MLS

GMI – Aura 4
20050601

GMI – MERRA Replay

MLS 20050601

GMI

GMI

0 40 80 120 160 200
N₂O Mixing Ratio [ppbv]

Note: the Aura5 run does about the same as the Aura4 run during this period.

Summary/Future Plans

2005040812

0 40 80 120 160 200
N₂O Mixing Ratio

VITA N₂O at 850 K on 18 April 2005

- FrIAC Lifecycle

- Spin-up (March –early April)
- Anticyclonic Phase (Early April – May)
- Shearing Phase (June – August)

- FrIAC Modeling

- GMI establishes the N₂O anomaly from 650-960 K.
- Peak N₂O values are too low.
- GMI-Aura4 and Aura5 show too much mixing as N₂O anomaly crosses the pole
- Aura4 and Aura5 runs lose the anomaly about a month too soon.
- MERRA-Replay simulates well at 850 K

- Future Plans

- Forecasting FrIAC with full GCM
- Examine FrIACs in other years
- Quantify mixing processes in summer stratosphere

Extras

GMI Vertical Resolution

- In the Aura4 run, the vertical resolution varies over the top and bottom half of the FrIAC.
 - ~2.7 km above 7 hPa
 - ~1.1 km below 15 hPa
- The Aura5 and MERRA-Replay provide more uniform vertical resolution

Shearing-Phase: early June - August

- Wind shears in both vertical and horizontal are rather weak
- Rough estimates were made of time for horizontal and vertical scales of FrIAC to reduce to resolution of GMI at 850 K (2° latitude, ~ 1.1 km).
- Horizontal: ~ 100 days, Vertical: ~ 75 days

Horizontal Shear in Angular Velocity
 $\sim O(0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{lon/day/}^\circ\text{lat})$

Vertical Shear in Zonal Wind
 $\sim O(0.4 \text{ m/s/km} = 0.0004 \text{ 1/s})$

5 hPa

10 hPa

20 hPa

Zonal Mean Heating Rate for March – August 2005